

Social Effects of Balkanization on the Peoples of Ethiopia's New Regional States

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Abstract

The balkanization of the Southern Nations, Nationalities, and Peoples' Region (SNNPR) is closely tied to Ethiopia's complex social and political history, characterized by centuries of conflict and a struggle for identity among its diverse ethnic groups. Southern Ethiopia is home to numerous cultural communities, many of which are small and have interacted with one another historically for thousands of years, highlighting both differences and similarities. The region was established in 1995 and was eventually dissolved in 2023. This has economic implications for the people within its constituency. To conduct this research, a mixed-methods approach combining both qualitative and quantitative techniques was employed, using face-to-face interviews and Likert scale questionnaires to collect open-ended narratives and trend data. The findings suggest that due to balkanization, there is a high rate of involuntary movement or relocation of civil servants with their families, resulting in children dropping out of school, disruption of social cohesion, and challenges to public service delivery and provision in the newly formed regional states in South Ethiopia. Therefore, the government must create favorable conditions for relocated workers and their families, who are involuntarily uprooted from their homes and social networks.

Keywords

Social effects, Balkanization, SNNPR, Family relocation, new regions, School dropout

Introduction

Southern states were incorporated into Ethiopia relatively recently. Most of these ethnic groups, with their recent histories of incorporation, are small and tend to live in the ethnically and

linguistically diverse southern regional state. As a result, ethnic groups from the South had been politically, economically, culturally, and linguistically marginalized until the introduction of ethnic federalism in 1995 (Erk, 2017).

With the change of government in 1991, fourteen transitional government regions were primarily created along ethnic lines, with the former SNNPR being formed from regions ranging from 7 to 11 (TGE, 1992) based on the constitutional provisions outlined in Proclamation 7/1992, Article 3/2 b. The merging of those five regions was more strongly enforced when the 1995 Constitution of the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia (FDRE) took effect. It also left room for regions to be dismembered to ensure their right to self-administration when need arises, as outlined in Articles 39 and 47. Nonetheless, challenges to implementing the right of self-determination have emerged due to unwarranted government and party interventions.

Despite strict governance by parties and governments to counter claims of self-determination, the ongoing struggles of ethnic groups have compelled them to modify their approaches. Kassa (2021) noted that the current number of regional states increased from nine to eleven, as two additional regional states emerged from the SNNPR in 2021. In November 2019, Sidama, one of the zones in SNNPR, voted to become an independent region and officially became a separate region in 2020. Next to it, four zones—Dawuro, Kaffa, Bench Shako, and Birab Omo—and one special Woreda, Konta, held a referendum and officially formed the South West Ethiopian Peoples Regional State (SWERS) from SNNPR in 2021.

Lately, two additional regional states, namely the South Ethiopia Regional State (SERS) and the Central Ethiopia Region State (CERS), have emerged from the SNNPR. Following the referendum conducted in the Wolayta, Gamo, Gofa, Gedeo, Konso zones, and Amaro, Derashe, Ale, and Basketo special woredas, the Prosperity Party declared that the SEPRS has been established. The referendum in Wolayta faced significant resistance because public options were not incorporated into the voting process. At the same time, Hadiya, Gurage, Silte, Kambata Tambaro, and Alaba zones, along with Yem special woreda, formed the CERS. Except for the Sidama, other ethnic groups were compelled to follow a "clustered structure" (Assefa et al., 2023) in regional state formation, characterized by multiple regional capital cities. This effectively balkanized the SNNPR into four separate regional states.

Balkanization as a word first emerged in the wake of World War I, referring to the fragmentation of the Balkans following the collapse of the Ottoman Empire. This term refers to the breakup of a multinational state into smaller, ethnically homogeneous components, often accompanied by political and economic instability (Zemon, 2018). The researcher applied this context to the internal disintegration of regional states within a federal system, as exemplified by the conditions encountered by SNNPR in the Ethiopian federal system.

The recent division of SNNPR into smaller regions was a result of long-standing demands for self-governance and recognition of ethnic identities within the federal system. Moreover, this process has exposed the failure to create an effective administrative structure that accommodates the diverse groups within SNNPR, leading to increased tensions and violent conflicts as groups compete for power and resources (Challachew, 2023). The move toward fragmentation is viewed by some as a dangerous precedent, indicating a possible unraveling of Ethiopia's federal order, which has historically aimed to balance ethnic diversity with centralized governance (Ethiopian Insight, 2020).

The historical background of the disintegration of SNNPR is closely linked to Ethiopia's complex social and political history, characterized by centuries of conflict and a struggle for identity among its diverse ethnic groups. Southern Ethiopia is home to dozens of cultural groups, many of which are small and have been in historical interaction for millennia, differing in various ways, yet also sharing similarities (Donham, 2000). The research experience confirms that southern Ethiopians have been accepted in anthropology in the last twenty-five years already: that "ethnic groups" and "culture" are cumulative historical constructions, and evolve not in isolation but in interaction, often within a regional or wider political-economic network (Abbink, 2000)

The dissolution of the Southern Nations, Nationalities, and Peoples' Region (SNNPR) into smaller regional states has had significant social consequences, particularly in terms of family dislocation resulting from the relocation of government offices and workplaces. This restructuring has disrupted livelihoods, separated families, and led to socio-economic instability, reflecting patterns seen in other examples of political fragmentation worldwide.

There are limited papers that examine social fragmentation, such as Leeson (2007), which examines the impact of state-created homogeneity on the ability of socially distant individuals to engage in trade. It shows that where the state is absent, socially distant agents adopt the customs, practices, and institutions of outsiders they desire to interact with. Pierson (1995) examines the impact of Federal institutions on social policy by influencing the strategies and power of social actors, creating new institutional actors, such as constituent units of the federation, and presenting challenges to shared decision-making. Moreover, Lloyd and Hannikainen (2022) examine the historical development of welfare states, focusing on how they promote social integration and mitigate societal fragmentation. It examines the interplay of political, social, economic, and institutional factors that led to the creation of welfare systems and their impact on achieving social peace. However, no study has been conducted to date on the social effects of regional state balkanization within a federal state structure. This paper fills the gap that has not yet been addressed.

Methodology

The research philosophy for this study is a pragmatic approach that combines both qualitative and quantitative methods to examine the social effects of regional state restructuring in Ethiopia. The study is grounded in social disorganization theory, which posits that rapid social and political changes can disrupt community stability, resulting in family dislocation and economic hardship. From this perspective, the theory provides valuable insights into how the reorganization of the SNNPR has affected families and livelihoods.

A mixed-methods approach combining both qualitative and quantitative methods was employed, utilizing face-to-face interviews and Likert scale questionnaires to collect open-ended narratives and gather trend data. This design provides a comprehensive view of the social factors involved in regional state balkanization. Twenty-one key informants, seven from each of the three multi-ethnic regional states—namely, SERS, CERS, and SWERS—were interviewed in the field. Sidama was excluded because its people were not relocated after becoming a regional state, including Hawassa, and civil servants stayed in their offices or were at least promoted. The participants included displaced families, government personnel, and community leaders to ensure the findings are generalizable. Themes such as family separation, economic hardship, and community adjustment emerged throughout the semi-structured interviews.

The social effect of balkanization was evaluated using a Likert-scale (1–5) questionnaire completed by 90 respondents, with 30 from each region. The effects on livelihood stability, family unity, and government support after restructuring raise important questions. Stratified purposive sampling was used to include participants from all three regional states and across various socio-economic groups. To analyze quantitative data, the mean and standard deviation were calculated. For qualitative data, frequency distributions and percentages were determined. Thematic analysis of the interview transcripts identified common themes, including family relocation, emotional distress, and institutional challenges. All participants provided consent, and measures were taken to ensure anonymity and voluntary participation. The study received approval from the appropriate institutional review board.

3. Social Effects of Balkanization on the People of the Newly Formed Regional States

The social effects of the Balkanization of the SNNPR in Ethiopia are multidimensional. Major effects include families relocating from their long-standing areas, children of displaced families dropping out of school, the disruption of social cohesion that has been established over time, and challenges to public service delivery and provision that affect both newcomers and residents. I will discuss each of these in detail by triangulating primary and secondary data.

3.1 Family relocation

Marshall et al. (2010) stated that relocation directly promotes more balanced regional economic growth through job creation, while also reducing overheating near the capital and the underuse of infrastructure and human resources in other areas. However, according to Rothe et al. (2014), relocation is an infrequent event for organizations; therefore, many organizations lack experience and knowledge on how to manage a successful move. This becomes even more critical when viewed from the perspective of the relocated individuals, as it presents significant challenges.

A high proportion of involuntary movement or displacement affects disadvantaged families, who, for various reasons, have limited choice in their living arrangements (Montgomery, 1960). Relocation presents prospective advantages, such as job progression and new experiences, although it also entails challenges like acclimating to a new area, leaving familiar settings, and potential financial burdens. Relocating often means leaving behind family, friends, familiar

surroundings, and cultural norms. Having to leave all of this behind can leave children feeling extremely vulnerable, due to the disruption of their sense of stability and routine.

The disintegration of the SNNPR in Ethiopia has resulted in significant family breakdown, primarily due to the relocation of its capital from Hawassa. It has upended the region’s socioeconomic landscape, with the hasty redistribution of government institutions and the transfer of civil servants to new regional capitals against their will, wrenching people from lives they had built. As Ethiopia has a very centralized civil service, such transfers were frequently made with little regard for family connections (Assefa et al., 2023).

A survey was conducted to assess the effect of the balkanization of family relocation from Hawassa to the new regional states. The results are shown in the table and the Histogram below.

The majority of respondents (82.2%) strongly agreed and (17.8%) agreed that families experienced relocation because of the disintegration of SNNPR. This overwhelming consensus suggests that job-induced displacement was pervasive, with large numbers of families relocated to different areas. The agreement level was very high, with a mean score of 4.82. A standard deviation (SD) of 0.384 shows low variability in the responses among the 90 participants. The relatively high mean value and low standard deviation together indicated that the impact was

dramatic and nearly universal among the respondents, suggesting an intense socio-economic upheaval at the household level. The data from informants complement this finding.

According to the informant in South Ethiopia,

Families are assigned to different cluster centers from Hawassa, where they have worked for about 30 years. Then the spouses may have been assigned to different centers. For example, a husband may be in Jinka, a wife in Dilla, which is about 500 kilometers away, and their children in Hawassa. In all three places, they rent houses and try to handle all necessary matters. However, their salary remains the same and is split among the three locations, with transportation costs to join at least once every 15 days accounting for most of their income. There is no alternative, and retiring a head is difficult because no economic base to support the responsibilities of children and other social duties, which are expensive in Ethiopia.

This report indicates that families have been divided, with some relocating to new administrative centers and others remaining behind for the sake of work, education, or property. The separation produces significant economic pressures, as two households—one in the city where the new job is located and another in the old city—further strain inadequate resources, according to informants. In addition to the difficulties in meeting financial needs, the psychosocial burden has been deep, especially for children and elderly dependents, who benefit from support from stable families/ (FSS, 2022). This indicates that balkanization is fragmenting families, which are considered the foundation of nation-building, and leading to social and economic crises.

The government reshuffle has also rearranged economic policies. The former regional capital, Hawassa, lost a significant amount of business and service interest as government offices with their lucrative budgets were relocated. Furthermore, the influx of labor to new capitals increased demand for housing and overall living expenses. This is similar to what Nigeria did in 1991 when it relocated its capital from Lagos to Abuja—a coercive removal. Families were broken apart, and tribal structures were weakened through coercive removals (Albert, 2017). This pattern was also similar to Sudan following the separation of South Sudan in 2011, when northern Sudanese civil servants working in the south were lifted from their jobs and sent on forced relocations, often leaving family behind as the citizenship of Sudan, or the separation of the South versus the North, remained unclear (Patey, 2014). In Ethiopia, such absence of

protections, particularly concerning protection from forced eviction, rights to family reunification, and cross-regional employment flexibility, has been a catalyst for heightened social instability. One of my informants from CERS mentioned that, while some families have reunited after a long time of ordeal, other victims have been estranged from their children.

The restructuring of the SNNPR has therefore mirrored social disintegration found in other riven countries. In the absence of policies that address forced displacement, family separation is likely to continue, undermining the social fabric. Following the examples of the world, Ethiopia should employ transitional safeguards against those harms.

3.2 Dropping out of school

The study by South et al. (2007), conducted in U.S. secondary schools, demonstrates that frequent residential migration and associated school mobility are significant factors contributing to educational failure. Although some differences in educational achievement for mobile versus non-mobile children are attributable to predisposing characteristics such as race/ethnicity, family SES, and family structure, a growing research literature over the past few decades demonstrates that student mobility, in particular school mobility, has adverse effects on myriad educational outcomes, including lower academic achievement and higher school drop-out rates.

Learning is a fundamental characteristic of human formation, deeply embedded in the cultural and social context. Moreover, as Ores (2012) underscores, human learning is social—children’s intellectual development is driven by their involvement in the knowledge and practices of others. However, this relies upon stability. The literature suggests that students who are not at risk of dropping out of high school are more likely to have family stability and access to social and financial resources. Evidence suggests that factors such as strong family support and good peer relationships are important, as high school completers tend to participate more in youth organizations compared to non-completers (Lim, 2008). When this stability is upended, the mental and academic ramifications for children can be severe, carrying long-term impacts on educational achievement and a sense of resilience and belonging.

In Ethiopia, the devolution of government, including the reorganization of SNNPR, has introduced significant social dislocation that has had severe consequences for children’s schooling. Civil servants and their families also experience being transferred from one post to

another, which few ever do. Consequently, many children are taken away from school, losing educational progress, which often results in irreversible cases. This is not exclusive to Ethiopia, as other regions that experience political decentralization have faced similar challenges with boundary shifts destabilizing education systems.

A survey was conducted to assess the effect of the Balkanization of SNNPR and related family relocation on child schooling. The results are presented in the table and the histogram.

56.7% agreed, and 43.3% strongly agreed. All respondents (100%) reported that a family move was the reason for children being out of school. A high mean score (4.43) and the skewness of the scores, which were skewed towards higher scores on the scale, have shown that the administrative change has negatively affected children's school attendance and continuity. This means that an educational network disequilibrium was an important social consequence of Balkanization. The low standard deviation value (0.498) indicates that the discomfort score is nearly uniformly distributed around the mean (4.43). Hence, we infer that most respondents were in agreement and firmly held their opinions, indicating that the data may be reliable and appropriate to reflect the universal perception or experience of the problem of school dropout among relocated children.

The fragmentation of SNNPR has increased financial stress on families, thereby pushing them further into poverty and making it difficult for them to maintain a quality education. Civil servant families, now struggling to maintain two households at two locations, have had to withdraw their children from private schools and send them to underfunded public schools. Not surprisingly, dropout rates have skyrocketed—from around 12.3% in 2012–2015 to 34.4% in 2020–2021, with even higher rates in marginalized parts of Ethiopia (Debebe, 2016). This has exacerbated educational inequalities already in place, with thousands of children left at a lifelong disadvantage.

Wood and Scarlata concur with the findings related to this, that

Frequent relocation was associated with higher rates of all measures of child dysfunction; 23% of children who moved frequently had repeated a grade against 12% of children who never or infrequently moved. Eighteen percent of children who moved frequently had four or more behavioral problems, against 7% of children who never or infrequently moved. The use of logistic regression to control for potential confounding covariates demonstrated that children who moved frequently were 77% more likely to be reported as having four or more behavioral problems, but no more likely to have experienced delays in growth or development or a learning disorder (Wood & Scarlata, 1993).

Therefore, family relocation and its related effects on children have a significant effect on the child's educational and socialization processes.

The human cost of this regional reorganization is clear. The children of transferred civil servants are often forced to transfer schools mid-year and, in many cases, are unable to re-enroll immediately due to bureaucratic delays. Missing or delayed school records complicate the situation additionally (FSS, 2022). Comparable though it is external secession, the case of Sudan following the independence of South Sudan (2011), when children of northern Sudanese civil servants were refused enrolment due to citizenship-related disagreements (Patey, 2014).

The logistical struggle aside, the psychological price paid by children is immense. When parents must choose between survival in the moment and education, with no opportunity for both, education often takes a back seat. Additionally, displaced children commonly experience social

alienation in new schools, being labelled as “outsiders,” increasing the risk of them dropping out of school. Such examples from history, such as the partition of India (1947), show that these disruptions result in long-term educational deficits both because of the trauma and of institutional disarray (Khan, 2017).

Some, however, have not ended so catastrophically. Germany’s unification (1990), for example, was accompanied by transitional education policies, curricular harmonization, and teacher support efforts aimed at limiting turmoil (Brockmann, 2011). Not so in Ethiopia. Unless concerted action is taken, the reorganization of SNNPR will generate a lost generation of educationally disadvantaged children. Ethiopia needs to learn from international experiences and establish frameworks for crisis-responsive policies to ensure students' right to education, while minimizing the costs associated with this administrative shift.

3.3 Eroded social cohesion

The administrative balkanization of Ethiopia’s SNNPR has adversely affected social cohesion, primarily through the relocation of civil servants and their families. It has not only torn apart existing communities but also created social cleavages that resemble the fallout from political fragmentation. The sudden departure of bureaucrats from the city of Hawassa disrupted longstanding relationships and connections that had been cultivated over multiple decades (FSS, 2022). This disruption is not only impacting relocated families, it is also dismantling the social capital of the communities in which they used to live, as well as the ones they now reside in, leaving rifts in social networks that last.

A survey was conducted to investigate the effect of SNNPR balkanization on the social cohesion of the relocated families. The results are presented in the table and the accompanying histogram.

Of the 90 respondents, 46.7% agreed, and 53.3% strongly agreed. That is, the rupture in the social fabric produced by a family move was reported by all the informants (100%). The mean of 4.53, combined with the tight distribution of responses to the left of ‘strongly agree’ and ‘agree’, indicates that bonds within communities and networks of friends and relatives diminished throughout the affected areas. This corresponds to a broader societal impact on the administrative and territorial reform. The low Standard Deviation (i.e., 0.502) indicates some consistency and strong agreement among respondents regarding the disruption of social cohesion as a result of migration. The largest proportion of participants (the majority) either agreed or strongly agreed with minimal variability.

Data reveal that such regional state formations disrupted social cohesion, neighborly relations, and trust within communities, and led to the mass dislocation and migration of families. The division of SNNPR through the forced relocation of families in connection with changes in workplace and administrative structures had disarticulated the established social networks, ruptured the community life, and shattered the social support networks. The data makes it clearer that, overwhelmingly, the respondents shared the same idea that “family relocation because of the balkanization of SNNPR” was a major disturbing factor affecting social cohesion.

According to Munton & Forster (2007), displaced families experience stress, sadness, and loneliness with the experience of being removed from their familiar communities and support systems. Moving from one work environment to another, coupled with relocating the family, can induce stress and influence performance at work. Making matters worse, financial constraints and restricted access to vital support services limit the ability to reestablish social relationships in new surroundings. Research indicates that high rates of family mobility are associated with adverse effects on children, including academic underachievement or the development of maladaptive behaviors (Wood & Scarlata, 1993).

Moreover, women bear an outsized cost in such relocations. Difficult trade-offs must be made between achieving a successful career and maintaining family stability (FSS, 2022) for many female public servants. There is evidence that women have more difficulty developing new relationships following migration compared to men (FSS, 2022). Although Baldrige et al. (2006) state that women managers are less willing to relocate, we also found that gender interacts with family attributes to dampen further a woman's willingness to relocate. This is not true in Ethiopia, where no alternative jobs, and thus people are relocated even to very distant areas. The breakdown of extended family has further increased the caregiving burden on women, leading to escalating gender disparities (Ben-Ishai, 2009).

The same was evident in Nigeria's state creation process, as administrative restructuring heavily impacted women due to their domestic and economic responsibilities (Suberu, 2023). The sociological effects of displacement are felt over generations. There is also greater social withdrawal and antisocial behavior reported in families with adolescents (Ben-Ishai, 2009). In addition, the decline of communal organizations has dilapidated the traditional form of transmitting social norms." These consequences resemble the long-lasting social disintegration observed among the displaced in post-division India (Khan, 2017).

Mitigation measures are suggested for the case where international patients are accepted. The approach to the reunification process in Germany is to invest in the 'social infrastructure' in order to create new networks (Brockmann, 2011). Reconciliation Villages in Rwanda are an example of purposefully designed communities aimed at restoring and reconnecting social relationships

(King, 2013). Moreover, restrictions on agents may be related to federal transfer systems in Canada, which allow networks of subscribers to be maintained when they move.

The experience in the SNNPR since then is a reminder that the social impacts of administrative dismemberment persist. Unless structured with exquisite care, such a reshuffling of the deck of lives will compound, rather than remedy, social disintegration across generations. Cross-national evidence suggests that policies aimed at enhancing social infrastructure and supporting families in transition have the most significant potential to improve these outcomes. Hence, policy-makers should focus on social unity as part of any further administrative reforms.

3.4 Challenges in Public Service Delivery

Service quality is essentially a function of public administration, and there are questions about the level of satisfaction at the local level regarding the performance of institutions (Mfene, 2009). The division of the SNNPR of Ethiopia into smaller regional states has posed a significant challenge in the realm of public service delivery, replicating global anxieties about the nature of government service (Farazmand, 2023). The establishment of new regional states, such as Sidama, SWERS, CERS, and SERS, has affected the provision of health, education, and infrastructure. The problem we add here is intra-capital competition and governance inefficiency. A series of policy options should be considered to address these issues, which echo problems in other countries related to decentralization and organizational fragmentation, and include discretion, decentralization, and national benchmarking.

A survey was conducted to assess the effect of balkanization on service provision and delivery in the newly established regional states in the South, related to the relocation of manpower. The results are displayed in the table and the Histogram below.

Of 90 responses, 71.1% agreed and 28.9% strongly agreed. This indicates that service provision and delivery were affected by the balkanization of SNNPR, resulting in family and workplace relocations for all participants (100%). The mean is 4.29, which implies that, in general, the relocation has affected service provision and delivery in the new regions, as indicated by the respondents who agreed or strongly agreed. The standard deviation is 0.456, indicating that the added values are tightly clustered around the mean. A majority of people share similar opinions, with little deviation among participants. The results indicate a considerable consensus that the move harmed service delivery, as evidenced by a relatively low level of disagreement among respondents, indicating that the adverse effect is strong and consistent.

Such data indicate that the movement of people and institutions has outpaced the capacity of new regional governments to deliver education, healthcare, infrastructure, and public administration. Administratively, balkanization created a new set of underfunded, understaffed, and organizationally weak regions, making the delivery of services more challenging and uneven. The table illustrates that the unanimous opinion of all eligible respondents was that the delivery of services in newly created regions was adversely affected by workplace relocations

following the balkanization of SNNPR, highlighting key issues in public service delivery. This is a result of administrative and institutional issues in the newly created regional states.

The transfer of government offices from Hawassa to regional capitals, including Arba Minch, Bonga, Wolaita Sodo, Hossana, and Butajira, has compounded service delivery, creating delays on condition of anonymity. Civil servant resistance to relocation to the less-developed capitals has led to capacity shortages (FDRE, 2023), and the reallocation of resources has created imbalances that hinder the adequate provision of services. There is a limited institutional capacity in the new regional governments, resulting in service delivery gaps, particularly in the health and education sectors, according to informants. The challenge of relocating public service facilities, previously concentrated in Hawassa, has compounded service inadequacies for the affected communities.

The informant in the South Ethiopia regional state narrated as follows.

When more people moved in from Hawassa, the former regional capital, it added to the existing population, creating struggles to access services. Most newly identified regional capitals are small towns with limited services. Houses for rent are scarce, the transportation system is inadequate, availability is limited, and there are few restaurants and cafes. Electric power is intermittent and may be unavailable for several days in towns such as Dimika. The water supply is very limited, making life challenging. This problem is also worse for the indigenous peoples of the town as demands increase with the growing population.

This highlights the challenges civil servants face in keeping their jobs despite current circumstances. However, it made it difficult for the customer to access and assess the quality of services.

Affinity cases would illustrate comparable problems arising from the disaggregation of administration. The creation of the 36 states in Nigeria since 1960 has, on the one hand, given minority groups a voice in government. However, on the other hand, it has eroded service delivery as smaller states struggle to mobilize adequate revenue (Suberu, 2023). The economic viability of such small administrative units continues to raise doubts, especially as the duplication of structures has increased costs without yielding concomitant benefits. The 2013 devolution of Kenya into 47 counties had mixed success, with some counties, such as Mombasa, showing improvement in governance, while others faced corruption and capacity challenges,

including Turkana (Cheeseman et al., 2016). The post-apartheid reconfiguration of provinces in South Africa has also been associated with unequal development, where rural provinces (e.g., the Eastern Cape) are less infrastructure-led than urban-based provinces (e.g., Gauteng).

In some cases, there are better lessons to be found. The service disruption following India's creation of Telangana state was only temporary (Tillin, 2019). However, the Democratic Republic of Congo experienced decentralization amidst largely unsuccessful conflict, as most provinces failed to deliver services (Englebert, 2009), and continued violence in provinces such as Kivu undermined the delivery of services (Autesserre, 2010). These comparative experiences demonstrate that fragmented SNNPR in Ethiopia poses a significant risk of leading to long-term service deficits without appropriate intervention.

The Ethiopian model teaches us what can go wrong with bureaucratic rearrangements ahead of time, without sufficient preparation, and thus undermines service delivery through the fragmentation of organizations and inadequate readiness. As cases from various countries tell us, decentralization succeeds when it is highly focused on inter-regional collaboration and capacity development. This article argues that in the absence of a strategy that ensures the state's role in delivering services reasonably well across the country, the establishment of new regional states could result in a decrease in service provision, rather than an improvement, for the millions of citizens who rely on these core government services. The experiences of other countries suggest that to mitigate the risk of service quality deterioration during a new round of service restructuring, planning, and phased implementation are essential.

Conclusion

The balkanization of SNNPR has caused lasting fear among the people of the newly formed multiethnic regional states. They were forced to relocate from Hawassa, the former capital of SNNPR, to very distant locations following the political decision to disband SNNPR. This has significant effects on civil servants and the people of the former SNNPR.

The uprooting of families as a result of the disintegration of the SNNP region has caused a massive social crisis. In most cases, whole communities were divided between two and sometimes three places, which caused old social relations and relationships to break down. Disintegration of communities has seriously impacted their social life, causing emotional distress, a narrowing of reciprocal support, and isolation on the part of affected families. Children, especially, have suffered from this tumult. Their progress through school was rudely interrupted. They were forced to switch schools, and indeed, many dropped out altogether. These difficulties can have far-reaching consequences for their life chances and psychological health.

Other vulnerable and dependent families, too — those whose jobs, child care, or emotional support depend on social networks — have faced similar challenges. The broader effects of this movement has been the disintegration of social structures and the ‘social capital’ that these communities had built up over decades and generations. Over time, the erosion of networks hinders the integration, trust, and cooperation essential for community life as families adapt to new, often unfamiliar, settings. These problems are compounded by significant public service delivery challenges. Displaced populations often experience interruptions or absences of essential services (e.g., health, education, water, and shelter). At the same time, host communities may also be unable to cope with the sudden pressure placed on their infrastructure and resources, causing tension and a general decline in the quality of services provided to all.

Given these extensive and profound effects, any political decision on territorial reconfiguration and relocation must be based on a well-founded planning approach. Governments should invest in comprehensive and well-resourced plans that provide for the organized and humane relocation of workers and their families.

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